

Synthesis of S-(4-Aryl-4H-1,2,4-Triazol-3yl) 2-Mercaptomethyl Benzimidazoles*

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Manuscript received 9 November 1976, accepted 15 April 1977

A number of benzimidazole derivatives were synthesised from 4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazolyl-3-mercaptoacetic acids by condensing with *o*-phenylenediamine and 4-chloro-*o*-phenylene diamine in presence of 4*N* hydrochloric acid. The 4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiols, S-(4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3yl) mercaptoacetic acids and S-(4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3yl) 2-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles have been screened for antibacterial, antituberculous and antifungal activities. Among them some of the acids showed weak antifungal activity against *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* at 50 mcg/ml concentration.

BENZIMIDAZOLE and its derivatives are known for their fungicidal, antibacterial and anthelmintic activities¹⁻³. Moreover 4H-1,2,4-triazole derivatives have been reported as antimicrobial agents^{4,5}. So, it has been proposed to synthesise the benzimidazole derivatives containing 4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazolyl moiety at 2-position. In this communication S-(4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3yl) 2-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles have been prepared by the following sequence of reactions. All these compounds have been screened for antibacterial, antituberculous and antifungal activities. Among them some of the acids showed weak antifungal activity against *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*.

1. 4-Arylthiosemicarbazides were cyclised with ethylformate in presence of sodium methoxide to get 3-mercapto-4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazoles (I).
2. The mercapto triazoles (I) were reacted with monochloroacetic acid to get S-(4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3yl) mercaptoacetic acids (II).
3. The 3-thioacetic acids (II) were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine and 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine to get the title compounds.

Biological data

The *in vitro* antibacterial, antituberculous and antifungal activities were studied by the serial dilution technique⁶. As the compounds are insoluble in broth, they were dissolved in dimethylformamide (DMF) and dilutions were made such that in no instance there was more than 1% DMF in the medium under study. It was confirmed that DMF at such concentrations had no inhibitory effect on the organisms under test. For antibacterial screening, the inoculated broth tubes were incubated at 37° for 24 hours and the dilution inhibiting the growth was noted. For antifungal screening, the inoculated broth tubes were incubated at 28° and the

state of growth was observed for 96 hours and the dilution showing no visible growth was noted. Antituberculous tests were carried out in Lownstien-Jenson media. Results were recorded after three weeks' incubation at 37° when tested at 50 mcg/ml concentration. These derivatives showed no inhibitory properties against the organisms.

Experimental

1. Preparation of 4-Aryl-3-mercapto-4H-1,2,4-triazoles :

Prepared by the method described earlier⁷.

4-Arylthiosemicarbazides (1 mol) and ethyl formate (1 mol) were added to sodium methoxide (1 mol) in absolute methanol, the mixture was refluxed for 8 hours; the solvent was removed and the residue was taken in water and acidified with acetic acid to precipitate 3-mercapto-4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazoles. The compounds were crystallised from aqueous alcohol in 68-70% yield.

2. Preparation of S-(4-Aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3yl) mercaptoacetic acids :

Prepared by the method described earlier⁸.

3-Mercapto-4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazoles (0.15 mol) were added to monochloroacetic acid (0.207 mol) in 104 ml sodium carbonate (0.414 mol) solution; the mixture was refluxed for 4-5 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid to precipitate acids. The compounds were crystallised from hot water.

3. Preparation of S-(4-Aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3yl) 2-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles :

Prepared by the method described earlier⁹.

*Presented at 26th Indian Pharmaceutical Congress, Dec. 28-30, 1974, Madras.

S-(4-Aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl) mercaptoacetic acids (0.03 mol) and *o*-phenylene diamine (0.02 mol) in 20 ml of 4*N* hydrochloric acid were refluxed for 8 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered; the filtrate was rendered alkaline with ammonia to obtain S-(4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl) 2-mercaptomethyl benzimidazoles. They were crystallised from aqueous acetic acid.

R = H; 2-, 3-, 4-CH₃; 2-, 3-, 4-OCH₃; 2-, 3-, 4-Cl;
 4-Br & I; 3-CF₃; 2,4-(CH₃)₂; 2-CH₃-4-Cl; 2-CH₃-5-Cl.
 X = H; Cl-

The compounds synthesised are listed in Tables 1-4.

TABLE 1—4-ARYL-3-MERCAPTO-4H-1,2,4-TRIAZOLE

S. No.	R	M.P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen % Found	Nitrogen % Calc.
1.	3-CH ₃	166-70	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S	21.2	21.9
2.	2-OCH ₃	188-90	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ OS	19.9	20.2
3.	3-OCH ₃	146-48	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ OS	19.8	20.2
4.	2-Cl	190-92	C ₈ H ₈ ClN ₃ S	20.1	19.8
5.	3-Cl	178-80	C ₈ H ₈ ClN ₃ S	20.8	19.8
6.	3-CF ₃	176-78	C ₉ H ₆ F ₃ N ₃ S	17.7	17.5
7.	4-Br	224-25	C ₈ H ₆ BrN ₃ S	16.9	16.4
8.	4-I	199-01	C ₈ H ₆ IN ₃ S	13.4	13.8
9.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	204-06	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ S	20.6	20.4
10.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	198-99	C ₉ H ₈ ClN ₃ S	18.4	18.6
11.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	176-80	C ₉ H ₈ ClN ₃ S	19.1	18.7

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 2—S-(4-ARYL-4H-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-3YL) MERCAPTOACETIC ACID

S. No.	R	M.P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen % Found	Nitrogen % Calc.
1.	H	208-09	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.6	17.8
2.	2-CH ₃	165-69	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.5	16.8
3.	3-CH ₃	176-78	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.5	16.8
4.	4-CH ₃	204-09	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.7	16.8
5.	2-OCH ₃	190-95	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.4	15.8
6.	3-OCH ₃	178-80	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.5	15.8
7.	4-OCH ₃	230-32	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.1	15.8
8.	2-Cl	160-62	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	15.6	15.5
9.	3-Cl	178-80	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	15.5	15.5
10.	4-Cl	230-32	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	15.7	15.5
11.	3-CF ₃	209-11	C ₁₁ H ₆ F ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	14.1	14.1
12.	4-Br	241-43	C ₁₀ H ₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	13.4	13.7
13.	4-I	248-50	C ₁₀ H ₆ IN ₃ O ₂ S	11.7	11.6
14.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	180-82	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.7	16.8
15.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	163-65	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	15.1	14.8
16.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	165-67	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	14.1	14.8

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 3—S-(4-ARYL-4H-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-3YL) 2-MERCAPTOMETHYL BENZIMIDAZOLE

S. No.	R	M.P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen % Found	Nitrogen % Calc.
1.	H	232-35	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₆ S	22.7	22.8
2.	2-CH ₃	169-71	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ S	22.0	21.8
3.	3-CH ₃	174-77	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ S	21.9	21.8
4.	4-CH ₃	188-94	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ S	22.4	21.8
5.	2-OCH ₃	228-30	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ OS	21.5	20.7
6.	3-OCH ₃	176-80	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ OS	20.7	20.7
7.	4-OCH ₃	227-29	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₆ OS	21.1	20.7
8.	2-Cl	211-13	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ S	20.4	20.5
9.	3-Cl	173-74	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ S	21.1	20.5
10.	4-Cl	212-14	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ S	20.4	20.5
11.	3-CF ₃	184-85	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ F ₃ N ₆ S	18.7	18.9
12.	4-Br	223-25	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ BrN ₆ S	17.4	18.1
13.	4-I	225-27	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ IN ₆ S	16.1	16.2
14.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	179-81	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₆ S	20.4	20.8
15.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	133-36	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ S	20.0	19.7
16.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	160-62	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ S	19.2	19.7

* All the melting points are uncorrected

TABLE 4—S-(4-ARYL-4H-1,2,4-TRIAZOL-3YL) 2-MERCAPTOMETHYL-5-CHLOROBENZIMIDAZOLE

S. No.	R	M.P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen % Found	Nitrogen % Calc.
1.	H	203-05	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₆ S	20.7	20.5
2.	2-CH ₃	159-61	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ S	19.5	19.7
3.	3-CH ₃	201-06	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ S	20.1	19.7
4.	4-CH ₃	209-11	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ S	20.0	19.7
5.	2-OCH ₃	164-68	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ OS	19.6	18.8
6.	3-OCH ₃	182-87	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ OS	18.8	18.8
7.	4-OCH ₃	210-12	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₆ OS	19.0	18.8
8.	2-Cl	187-89	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	18.7	18.6
9.	3-Cl	218-20	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	19.1	18.6
10.	4-Cl	209-10	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	19.1	18.6
11.	3-CF ₃	145-47	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ F ₃ ClN ₆ S	17.4	17.3
12.	4-Br	213-15	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrClN ₆ S	16.2	16.6
13.	4-I	227-28	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClIN ₆ S	15.7	15.0
14.	2,4-(CH ₃) ₂	212-14	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ ClN ₆ S	19.0	18.9
15.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	203-05	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	17.6	18.0
16.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	165-67	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ S	18.4	18.0

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. V. Srinivasan, Director, Sarabhai Research Centre for his keen interest in the work.

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